

```

GET
  FILE='D:\MY PhD JOURNEY\SEMESTER 6\DATA HIPERTENSI KASUS DAN KONTROL\SKI 2023\Cici Apriza
Yanti_var_SKI_2023._1.sav'.
DATASET NAME DataSet1 WINDOW=FRONT.
USE ALL.
COMPUTE filter_$=(B18 = 0).
VARIABLE LABELS filter_$ 'B18 = 0 (FILTER)'.
VALUE LABELS filter_$ 0 'Not Selected' 1 'Selected'.
FORMATS filter_$ (f1.0).
FILTER BY filter_$.
EXECUTE.
USE ALL.
COMPUTE filter_$=(B18 > 0).
VARIABLE LABELS filter_$ 'B18 > 0 (FILTER)'.
VALUE LABELS filter_$ 0 'Not Selected' 1 'Selected'.
FORMATS filter_$ (f1.0).
FILTER BY filter_$.
EXECUTE.
FREQUENCIES VARIABLES=B1R1 B4K4 B18 Sweet_Food Salty_Food Fatty_Food Instant_Noodles SweerGR
  SweetFood SaltyFood SaltyFoodGr FattyFoodGr InstantNoodles InstantNoodlesGr C_SweetFood
  C_SaltyFoodGr C_FattyFoodGr C_InstantNoodlesGr
/ORDER=ANALYSIS.

```

Frequencies

		Notes
Output Created		24-OCT-2024 15:07:08
Comments		
Input	Data	D:\MY PhD JOURNEY\SEMESTER 6\DATA HIPERTENSI KASUS DAN KONTROL\SKI 2023\Cici Apriza Yanti_var_SKI_2023._1.sav
	Active Dataset	DataSet1
	File Label	SKI2023_DICT
	Filter	B18 > 0 (FILTER)
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	638180
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics are based on all cases with valid data.
Syntax		FREQUENCIES VARIABLES=B1R1 B4K4 B18 Sweet_Food Salty_Food Fatty_Food Instant_Noodles SweerGR SweetFood SaltyFood SaltyFoodGr FattyFoodGr InstantNoodles InstantNoodlesGr C_SweetFood C_SaltyFoodGr C_FattyFoodGr C_InstantNoodlesGr /ORDER=ANALYSIS.

Resources	Processor Time	00:00:04.24
	Elapsed Time	00:00:04.03

[DataSet1] D:\MY PhD JOURNEY\SEMESTER 6\DATA HIPERTENSI KASUS DAN KONTROL\SKI 2023\Cici Apriza Yanti_var_SKI_2023._1.sav

Frequency Table

		1.Provinsi			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Aceh	26681	4.2	4.2	4.2
	Sumatera Utara	40558	6.4	6.4	10.5
	Sumatera Barat	24910	3.9	3.9	14.4
	Riau	16126	2.5	2.5	17.0
	Jambi	14305	2.2	2.2	19.2
	Sumatera Selatan	24669	3.9	3.9	23.1
	Bengkulu	12520	2.0	2.0	25.0
	Lampung	20828	3.3	3.3	28.3
	Kep.Bangka Belitung	9708	1.5	1.5	29.8
	Kepulauan Riau	8382	1.3	1.3	31.1
	DKI Jakarta	9226	1.4	1.4	32.6
	Jawa Barat	37561	5.9	5.9	38.5
	Jawa Tengah	55313	8.7	8.7	47.1
	DI Yogyakarta	8473	1.3	1.3	48.5
	Jawa Timur	59219	9.3	9.3	57.7
	Banten	11227	1.8	1.8	59.5

Bali	14809	2.3	2.3	61.8
Nusa Tenggara Barat	13548	2.1	2.1	63.9
Nusa Tenggara Timur	25349	4.0	4.0	67.9
Kalimantan Barat	14839	2.3	2.3	70.2
Kalimantan Tengah	12830	2.0	2.0	72.2
Kalimantan Selatan	16522	2.6	2.6	74.8
Kalimantan Timur	10979	1.7	1.7	76.6
Kalimantan Utara	4649	.7	.7	77.3
Sulawesi Utara	16070	2.5	2.5	79.8
Sulawesi Tengah	14440	2.3	2.3	82.1
Sulawesi Selatan	33221	5.2	5.2	87.3
Sulawesi Tenggara	18582	2.9	2.9	90.2
Gorontalo	7076	1.1	1.1	91.3
Sulawesi Barat	6935	1.1	1.1	92.4
Maluku	11816	1.9	1.9	94.2
Maluku Utara	10137	1.6	1.6	95.8
Papua Barat	5369	.8	.8	96.7
Papua Barat Daya	4389	.7	.7	97.3
Papua	6924	1.1	1.1	98.4
Papua Selatan	2943	.5	.5	98.9
Papua Tengah	3904	.6	.6	99.5
Papua Pegunungan	3143	.5	.5	100.0
Total	638180	100.0	100.0	

4. Jenis Kelamin

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Laki-laki	291420	45.7	45.7	45.7
	Prempuan	346760	54.3	54.3	100.0
Total		638180	100.0	100.0	

B18. Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Tidak	584512	91.6	91.6	91.6
	Ya	53668	8.4	8.4	100.0
Total		638180	100.0	100.0	

SweetFood

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	<7x / week	4665	.7	.7	.7
	>4 x / week	23548	3.7	3.7	4.4
	<3 x / week	146164	22.9	22.9	27.3
	< 2 x / week	331319	51.9	51.9	79.2
	<1 x / week	123634	19.4	19.4	98.6
	Never	8850	1.4	1.4	100.0
	Total	638180	100.0	100.0	

SaltyFoodGr

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	<7x / week	9753	1.5	1.5	1.5
	>4 x / week	57287	9.0	9.0	10.5
	<3 x / week	198901	31.2	31.2	41.7
	< 2 x / week	256928	40.3	40.3	81.9
	<1 x / week	101173	15.9	15.9	97.8
	Never	14138	2.2	2.2	100.0
	Total	638180	100.0	100.0	

FattyFoodGr

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	<7x / week	10916	1.7	1.7	1.7
	>4 x / week	62739	9.8	9.8	11.5
	<3 x / week	229868	36.0	36.0	47.6
	< 2 x / week	248058	38.9	38.9	86.4
	<1 x / week	77765	12.2	12.2	98.6
	Never	8834	1.4	1.4	100.0
	Total	638180	100.0	100.0	

InstantNoodlesGr

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	<7x / week	17328	2.7	2.7	2.7
	>4 x / week	186543	29.2	29.2	31.9
	<3 x / week	275283	43.1	43.1	75.1
	< 2 x / week	99806	15.6	15.6	90.7
	<1 x / week	46507	7.3	7.3	98.0
	Never	12713	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	638180	100.0	100.0	

C SweetFood

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	8850	1.4	1.4	1.4
	Yes	629330	98.6	98.6	100.0
	Total	638180	100.0	100.0	

C_SaltyFoodGr

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	14138	2.2	2.2	2.2
	Yes	624042	97.8	97.8	100.0
	Total	638180	100.0	100.0	

C FattyFoodGr

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	8834	1.4	1.4
	Yes	629346	98.6	100.0
	Total	638180	100.0	100.0

C InstantNoodlesGr

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No	12713	2.0	2.0
	Yes	625467	98.0	100.0
	Total	638180	100.0	100.0

CROSSTABS

```
/TABLES=C_SweetFood C_SaltyFoodGr C_FattyFoodGr C_InstantNoodlesGr BY B18  
/FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES  
/STATISTICS=CHISQ RISK  
/CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW  
/COUNT ROUND CELL.
```

Crosstabs

Notes

Output Created		24-OCT-2024 15:08:36
Comments		
Input	Data	D:\MY PhD JOURNEY\SEMESTER 6\DATA HIPERTENSI KASUS DAN KONTROL\SKI 2023\Cici Apriza Yanti_var_SKI_2023._1.sav
	Active Dataset	DataSet1
	File Label	SKI2023_DICT
	Filter	B18 > 0 (FILTER)
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	638180
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics for each table are based on all the cases with valid data in the specified range(s) for all variables in each table.
Syntax		CROSSTABS /TABLES=C_SweetFood C_SaltyFoodGr C_FattyFoodGr C_InstantNoodlesGr BY B18 /FORMAT=AVALUE TABLES /STATISTICS=CHISQ RISK /CELLS=COUNT EXPECTED ROW /COUNT ROUND CELL.
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:03.66
	Elapsed Time	00:00:03.43
	Dimensions Requested	2
	Cells Available	349496

Case Processing Summary

	Cases					
	Valid		Missing		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
C_SweetFood * B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter?	638180	100.0%	0	0.0%	638180	100.0%
C_SaltyFoodGr * B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter?	638180	100.0%	0	0.0%	638180	100.0%
C_FattyFoodGr * B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter?	638180	100.0%	0	0.0%	638180	100.0%
C_InstantNoodlesGr * B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter?	638180	100.0%	0	0.0%	638180	100.0%

C_SweetFood * B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter?

Crosstab

			B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter?		Total
			Tidak	Ya	
C_SweetFood	No	Count	7034	1816	8850
		Expected Count	8105.8	744.2	8850.0
		% within C_SweetFood	79.5%	20.5%	100.0%
	Yes	Count	577478	51852	629330
		Expected Count	576406.2	52923.8	629330.0
		% within C_SweetFood	91.8%	8.2%	100.0%
Total	Count	584512	53668	638180	
	Expected Count	584512.0	53668.0	638180.0	
	% within C_SweetFood	91.6%	8.4%	100.0%	

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1708.798 ^a	1	.000		
Continuity Correction ^b	1707.204	1	.000		
Likelihood Ratio	1268.561	1	.000		
Fisher's Exact Test				.000	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	1708.795	1	.000		
N of Valid Cases	638180				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 744.24.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Risk Estimate

	Value	95% Confidence Interval	
		Lower	Upper
Odds Ratio for C_SweetFood (No / Yes)	.348	.330	.366
For cohort B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter? = Tidak	.866	.857	.875
For cohort B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter? = Ya	2.490	2.388	2.597
N of Valid Cases	638180		

C_SaltyFoodGr * B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter?

Crosstab

			B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter?		Total
			Tidak	Ya	
C_SaltyFoodGr	No	Count	12118	2020	14138
		Expected Count	12949.1	1188.9	14138.0
		% within C_SaltyFoodGr	85.7%	14.3%	100.0%
	Yes	Count	572394	51648	624042
		Expected Count	571562.9	52479.1	624042.0
		% within C_SaltyFoodGr	91.7%	8.3%	100.0%
Total		Count	584512	53668	638180
		Expected Count	584512.0	53668.0	638180.0
		% within C_SaltyFoodGr	91.6%	8.4%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	648.609 ^a	1	.000		
Continuity Correction ^b	647.829	1	.000		
Likelihood Ratio	548.176	1	.000		
Fisher's Exact Test				.000	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	648.608	1	.000		
N of Valid Cases	638180				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1188.94.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Risk Estimate

	Value	95% Confidence Interval	
		Lower	Upper
Odds Ratio for C_SaltyFoodGr (No / Yes)	.541	.516	.568
For cohort B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter? = Tidak	.934	.928	.941
For cohort B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter? = Ya	1.726	1.657	1.799
N of Valid Cases	638180		

C_FattyFoodGr * B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter?

Crosstab

			B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter?		Total
			Tidak	Ya	
C_FattyFoodGr	No	Count	7583	1251	8834
		Expected Count	8091.1	742.9	8834.0
		% within C_FattyFoodGr	85.8%	14.2%	100.0%
	Yes	Count	576929	52417	629346
		Expected Count	576420.9	52925.1	629346.0
		% within C_FattyFoodGr	91.7%	8.3%	100.0%
Total	Count	584512	53668	638180	
	Expected Count	584512.0	53668.0	638180.0	
	% within C_FattyFoodGr	91.6%	8.4%	100.0%	

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	384.746 ^a	1	.000		
Continuity Correction ^b	383.989	1	.000		
Likelihood Ratio	325.625	1	.000		
Fisher's Exact Test				.000	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	384.746	1	.000		
N of Valid Cases	638180				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 742.90.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Risk Estimate

	Value	95% Confidence Interval	
		Lower	Upper
Odds Ratio for C_FattyFoodGr (No / Yes)	.551	.518	.585
For cohort B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter? = Tidak	.936	.928	.944
For cohort B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter? = Ya	1.700	1.614	1.791
N of Valid Cases	638180		

C_InstantNoodlesGr * B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter?

Crosstab

			B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter?		Total
			Tidak	Ya	
C_InstantNoodlesGr	No	Count	10733	1980	12713
		Expected Count	11643.9	1069.1	12713.0
		% within C_InstantNoodlesGr	84.4%	15.6%	100.0%
	Yes	Count	573779	51688	625467
		Expected Count	572868.1	52598.9	625467.0
		% within C_InstantNoodlesGr	91.7%	8.3%	100.0%
Total		Count	584512	53668	638180
		Expected Count	584512.0	53668.0	638180.0
		% within C_InstantNoodlesGr	91.6%	8.4%	100.0%

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2- sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	864.580 ^a	1	.000		
Continuity Correction ^b	863.631	1	.000		
Likelihood Ratio	709.167	1	.000		
Fisher's Exact Test				.000	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	864.579	1	.000		
N of Valid Cases	638180				

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1069.10.

b. Computed only for a 2x2 table

Risk Estimate

	Value	95% Confidence Interval	
		Lower	Upper
Odds Ratio for C_ InstantNoodlesGr (No / Yes)	.488	.465	.513
For cohort B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter? = Tidak	.920	.913	.927
For cohort B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter? = Ya	1.885	1.808	1.964
N of Valid Cases	638180		

LOGISTIC REGRESSION VARIABLES B18

/METHOD=ENTER C_SweetFood C_SaltyFoodGr C_FattyFoodGr C_ InstantNoodlesGr

/PRINT=CI(95)

/CRITERIA=PIN(0.05) POUT(0.10) ITERATE(20) CUT(0.5).

Logistic Regression

Notes

Output Created		24-OCT-2024 15:09:23
Comments		
Input	Data	D:\MY PhD JOURNEY\SEMESTER 6\DATA HIPERTENSI KASUS DAN KONTROL\SKI 2023\Cici Apriza Yanti_var_SKI_2023._1.sav
	Active Dataset	DataSet1
	File Label	SKI2023_DICT
	Filter	B18 > 0 (FILTER)
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	638180
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing
Syntax		LOGISTIC REGRESSION VARIABLES B18 /METHOD=ENTER C_SweetFood C_SaltyFoodGr C_FattyFoodGr C_InstantNoodlesGr /PRINT=C(95) /CRITERIA=PIN(0.05) POUT(0.10) ITERATE(20) CUT(0.5).
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:09.77
	Elapsed Time	00:00:09.59

Case Processing Summary

Unweighted Cases ^a		N	Percent
Selected Cases	Included in Analysis	638180	100.0
	Missing Cases	0	.0
	Total	638180	100.0
Unselected Cases		0	.0
Total		638180	100.0

a. If weight is in effect, see classification table for the total number of cases.

Dependent Variable Encoding

Original Value	Internal Value
Tidak	0
Ya	1

Block 0: Beginning Block

Classification Table^{a,b}

	Observed	Predicted		
		B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter?		Percentage Correct
		Tidak	Ya	
Step 0	B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter?	Tidak	Ya	
		584512	0	100.0
		53668	0	.0
	Overall Percentage			91.6

a. Constant is included in the model.

b. The cut value is .500

Variables in the Equation

	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)
Step 0 Constant	-2.388	.005	280297.930	1	.000	.092

Variables not in the Equation

	Score	df	Sig.
Step 0 Variables C_SweetFood	1708.798	1	.000
C_SaltyFoodGr	648.609	1	.000
C_FattyFoodGr	384.746	1	.000
C_InstantNoodlesGr	864.580	1	.000
Overall Statistics	2752.558	4	.000

Block 1: Method = Enter

Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients

	Chi-square	df	Sig.
Step 1 Step	2099.451	4	.000
Block	2099.451	4	.000
Model	2099.451	4	.000

Model Summary

Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	366334.039 ^a	.003	.007

a. Estimation terminated at iteration number 5 because parameter estimates changed by less than .001.

Classification Table^a

	Observed	Predicted			
		B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter?		Percentage Correct	
		Tidak	Ya		
Step 1	B18.Apakah [NAMA] pernah didiagnosis menderita hipertensi oleh dokter?	Tidak	584512	0	100.0
		Ya	53668	0	.0
	Overall Percentage				91.6

a. The cut value is .500

Variables in the Equation

	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I. for EXP(B)		
							Lower	Upper	
Step 1 ^a	C_SweetFood	-.888	.028	1032.750	1	.000	.411	.390	.434
	C_SaltyFoodGr	-.397	.027	212.451	1	.000	.672	.637	.709
	C_FattyFoodGr	-.187	.035	29.235	1	.000	.829	.775	.888
	C_InstantNoodlesGr	-.566	.026	492.020	1	.000	.568	.540	.597
	Constant	-.398	.043	86.398	1	.000	.672		

a. Variable(s) entered on step 1: C_SweetFood, C_SaltyFoodGr, C_FattyFoodGr, C_InstantNoodlesGr.